

QUIZ**LAST NAME: IGBODIKA****FIRST NAME: VIRTUOUS****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: PROF CLEENEWERCK****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. Which of the following options are correct of EUCLID writing style?
 - Response Papers are to demonstrate your understanding of the period materials while Major Papers are to test your suitability to write a dissertation.
 - EUCLID recommends the use of Turabian Style in academic writing and the use of American English.¹**
 - Response and major paper templates are a guide to how your assignments should look; you may change it to suite the peculiarity of your preference.
 - Major papers are double spaced, academic and do not use in-text or parenthetical referencing, but footnote referencing. You are free to choose either the US or UK writing standard.²**

¹ EUCLID. "ACA-401 Course pack". Washington DC, 2015, accessed June 10, 2019, <http://www.lc.unsw.edu.au>

² Laurent Cleenewerck. "Basic ACA-401 Tutorial." Euclid University. June 2019. Video, 14:34. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/> ; EUCLID, n.a.

2. **Citation in academic writing is critical for a number of reasons. The statements below discuss these reasons. Which of the following is correct?**

- Citations are important in fostering further research. Readers will look to your citations in taking forward your research or even venturing into theirs.** ³
- Citation provides readers with understanding of your research tradition; as it helps them situate your research within the larger community in your research field.** ⁴
- Proper citation makes your readers judge your research true; it proves that your research findings are accurate and reliable.
- It is critical to cite sources you consult in order to give credit to work that is done by others. Not citing sources consulted can result in plagiarism.**⁵

3. **What statement(s) below are correct regarding writing styles?**

- For the US standard of writing, punctuation marks are placed inside the inverted commas and quotation marks. For in-text citation, when authors' names are cited in the sentence, the year is written after the name, and the page number at the end of the sentence.**⁶
- Turabian style recommends that for in-text citations, the Authors' name, year and page numbers should be mentioned when it is a direct quote, and only author and date should be mentioned when the writer is referring to the authors' idea.

³ Kate, Turabian L. A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 86.

⁴ Ibid, 86

⁵ Ibid, 86

⁶ EUCLID, 8, n.a

- Consistency in the use of writing styles is important. However, because of the minor differences in UK and US spellings of words these can be used interchangeably.
 - Commas should be used to separate a clause and supporting phrase of a sentence, and to indicate a pause. In separating items in a list, commas should be put after each item including the second to the last one, followed by an 'and' to reduce ambiguity.⁷**
4. **Which of the statements below best explains components and process in building an argument?**
- A story board, an outline, a dissertation holder and a physical shelf are components that support you in managing your raw data for analysis when building your argument.
 - The research problem is the problem that your research is based on and so the focal point of your argument. The research question is the question your entire research will be hinged on while your argument will be built around your research hypothesis.
 - Your hypothesis is technically your claim which you will support with your reasons and have evidence for those reasons. In doing these, it is important to evaluate other views on your claim and seek to explain the principles that make your reasons relevant.⁸**
 - In assembling your argument, you will need to collect and analyze data from surveys, secondary data, interviews, focus group discussion and journals, depending on which methods you used to collect data.
5. **Give one reason why is it important for a researcher to equally look for sources that contradict his or her view.**

⁷ EUCLID, 3&7.

⁸ Turabian, 41&42

- It is important to consult materials that contradict a researchers' views order to demonstrate that you have consulted widely;
- It is critical to find ways to disprove contrary arguments in the light of the research findings;
- It is important for researchers for respond to opposing views that in order to gain the credibility of readers.⁹**
- Learning more on contrary opinions helps us know what not to focus your arguments on.

6. **In not more than three sentences, explain what a PhD student requires in order to complete a dissertation.**

- A doctorate student is unlikely to complete his dissertation if he does not have previous experience in research. It is also critical for a PhD student to have a study group, make arrangements for a physical space and materials such as a library, folders, story board and others if he will complete his dissertation.
- If a student does not sharpen or develop the skill of critical thinking, have the ability to systematically plan his research process step by step, use problem solving skills, and take practical decisions at every point in time, there are chances that he will not complete his dissertation.¹⁰**
- If a PhD student will complete his dissertation, it is important to have a supervisor that he connects with, the tutor may not necessarily be an expert in his field but has an emotional connection enough to give the needed guidance and support.
- To support the interest that is required to complete a PhD dissertation, it is important to choose a topic in an area of interest or field of work.

⁹ Turabian, 25.

¹⁰ Linda Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Thousand Oaks CA: Sage 2008), 20.

Breaking down your research into manageable phases and setting a tight schedule is also a determinant of completion.

7. **Describe in not more than three sentences, the rationale and the features of the methodology chapter of a Dissertation.**

- The methodology chapter is the most critical chapter in your dissertation. It shows how you have planned to execute your research by breaking it down to chapters, giving justifications for the conceptual framework derived from literature, and highlighting the potential of the research as well as its limitations.
- The methodology chapter is aimed at giving clarity to how you plan to execute your research. The chapter explains and justifies the approach or traditions you will be using, backed by literature. It is also critical that the chapter shows how you were journaling your journey, the reasons you changed approaches, methods or traditions, and how your thinking evolved.¹¹**
- The methodology chapter explains the research in great detail. It compares similar researches, aims to find the most plausible methodology to adopt, and explains the selected method in detail. It serves as a bridge between the literature review and the findings chapter.
- The methodology chapter defines feasible timelines for the research, makes some predictions of the outcome of the research based on the 'field test'. It carries out a literature review of relevant research topics and selects the best approach from literature which will be used in the research.

8. **The research problem, purpose and research questions are the building blocks of any research. Explain what they are and how they interrelate.**

¹¹ Bloomberg and Volpe, 68 & 72.

- The research problem is the topic of your dissertation, it is what a researcher seeks to carry out his research. The research purpose is the reason the topic was selected; it is simply the justification for the selected topic; the research questions are the research purpose broken down in questions. The questions break the problem in bite sizes in order to help the reader understand the purpose and rationale more deeply.
- As the building block of the dissertation; the research problem, purpose and questions constitute the research proposal. The research problem states the validity of the problem which will be further explained by the purpose of choice of problem. The research questions will draw from the purpose to help break down the research in manageable bits.
- The research problem is the problem that your research seeks to bring more understanding to. It should be a worthy area that indicates the need for the study. While the research purpose tells the objective of the research - how the researcher intends to go about the research - the research questions are questions you ask that will shed more light on the problem when answered.¹²**
- The research problem, purpose and questions make up the dissertation proposal. The research problem draws problems from existing gaps in literature in order to fill the gaps, the purpose explains why filling such a gap is necessary while the research questions are components of the research problem that are broken down into questions that will guide the research.

9. Why is coding important in qualitative research?

- Coding is a data collection method that makes it easy for the researcher to identify the data that is relevant to his research topic.
- Coding is a system of grouping findings according to quantitative data that is available on the research questions. These groupings make for easier analysis of the findings.

¹² Bloomberg and Volpe, 34-37.

- Coding is a simple method used to analyze qualitative data used in a research.
- Coding is a system of classification; it helps the researcher to note what is of significance by organizing his qualitative data through segmenting and labelling them to make analysis easier.**¹³

10. Which of the following statements are true of writing a qualitative research proposal?

- To write a good qualitative research proposal, you will need to have the experience of having written and published several academic papers.
- To write a good qualitative research proposal it is critical to have gathered all the data you need for your analysis in order to adequately make informed inference on the findings.
- To write a good qualitative research proposal you will need a researchable problem and a good understanding of what qualitative research is.**¹⁴
- To write a good qualitative research proposal you must have a final research question that is unlikely to change during the course of the research.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda D. and Volpe, Marie. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. Thousand Oaks CA: Sage, 2008.

EUCLID. *ACA-401 Course pack*. Washington DC, 2015. Accessed June 10, 2019).
<http://www.lc.unsw.edu.au>.

¹³ Bloomberg and Volpe, 102.

¹⁴ Ibid, 12.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013.

Cleenewerck, Laurent. "Basic ACA-401 Tutorial." EUCLID University. June 2019. Video, 14:34. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/>.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.